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Case study of the socio-economic impacts of an Ion Beam Analysis facility in Brazil.

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Abstract: This article examines the socioeconomic impacts of the Ion Beam Analysis (IBA) Laboratory at the University of São Paulo (LAMFI-USP), which has been in operation since 1992. The use of accelerated ion beams for materials analysis at USP has led to technological advancements in various fields, including environmental science, cultural heritage preservation, archaeology, and medical and biological applications, significantly contributing to scientific research, technological development, and human resource training in Brazil. The innovations generated at LAMFI-USP encompass advancements in IBA techniques, as well as collaborative research in areas such as fusion reactors, solar cells, environmental monitoring, archaeology, healthcare, microelectronics, and energy. By supporting research in both basic and applied sciences, the laboratory has fostered interdisciplinary collaboration, generating socioeconomic benefits and enhancing Brazil's scientific competitiveness on a global scale. This work also explores the hypothesis that the socioeconomic impact of a research laboratory can, as a first approximation, be estimated by the square of its corresponding Technology Readiness Level (TRL). Although the TRL is not a direct metric of socioeconomic impact, each level incorporates the cumulative effort and societal value required to achieve that level of technological maturity. As a consequence, a Socio-Economic Impact Index (SEII) is proposed to both evaluate the broader societal impact of the laboratory and assist in ranking ongoing research activities as part of an auxiliary assessment of its operations.

Keywords: Socio-economic impact, Ion Beam Analysis, IBA, TRL.

1. INTRODUCTION

The topic of this paper was initially inspired by a workshop held at the IAEA (2023) about the Socio-economic Benefits of Accelerator-based Techniques. During the four-day event, a multidisciplinary panel discussed the socio-economic benefits of small particle accelerators, from e-beams and heavy ion cyclotrons to low energy electrostatic ion accelerators.

This paper, offers an insight and reviews the socio-economic outcomes of the research conducted at LAMFI-USP, an Ion Beam Analysis facility established at the University of São Paulo in 1989. In section 3, we further explore an attempt to relate the Technological Readiness Level (TRL) of the various outcomes to their socio-economic impact, a simplified, first-order approximation.

According to Coccia (2018), the socio-economic impacts of science are the tangible effects of research and innovation on society's well-being and the economy. These include improvements in quality of life, economic growth, job creation, and environmental sustainability. Science drives productivity, creates new markets, and helps address common challenges such as improving health, enhancing food production, and mitigating environmental impacts. It also promotes a more knowledgeable society and makes countries more competitive by attracting investment and supporting international trade. The socio-economic impacts of science may vary across regions and countries, depending on factors such as investment in research and technical development, access to education, and science and technology policies. In developed countries, science contributes to the growth of local industries through the development of novel materials, new processes, and technological breakthroughs. In emerging countries like Brazil, science primarily impacts the preparation of human resources, which is perhaps its most valuable outcome. Nonetheless, science generally has a transformative effect on societies by driving progress, reducing inequality, and enhancing the well-being of the population.

Nowadays, the socio-economic impacts of science, once considered undeniable, are facing increased scrutiny. Governments are under pressure to justify (and possibly reduce) expenditures on science and education. These trends are also evident in Brazil, with growing hostility toward public higher education, driven by fake news and discriminatory comments about life in Brazilian public universities. As a result, universities are now urged to make their socio-economic impact more evident and to improve communication, engaging more actively with society and the political class, who ultimately endorses the funding of research. These criticisms are not new. In 1939, at the onset of World War II, Bernal (1939) already argued that while science once believed to lead to continuous progress of society, could also be used for destructive and wasteful purposes. For the first time, voices were raised calling for the cessation of scientific research as a means of preserving a tolerable civilization. Scientists have since been compelled to consider how their work is connected with social and economic developments.

In this context, the socio-economic impacts of low and high energy ion accelerators and related technologies, though indirect, are significant. Ion accelerators impact scientific research, technological advancements, medical applications, materials science, environmental monitoring, education, and science outreach. Additionally, they encourage innovation and entrepreneurship, international collaborations, and the development of local industries. Ion Beam Analysis (IBA), an extremely sensitive set of analytical tools for the characterization of materials and thin films using small ion accelerators (<3MV), has been increasingly utilized since its use in air pollution research in 1970, anticipating the current environmental challenges, such as climate changes and global

pollution (Johansson, Akselsson, and Johansson Johansson, 1970). IBA is also being used to study archaeological and artistic objects, with scientific inquiries often related to identifying their elemental or chemical composition to infer their environment or origin. Accelerators can also modify materials, some of biomedical interest, such as enhancing the surfaces of prostheses for better and faster osseointegration. Small accelerators play a role in assessing radiation-tolerant microcircuits, which impact high-tech fields like avionics, the space industry, and autonomous vehicles. IBA is a valuable tool for the quality control (or diagnostics) of high-tech materials (Charisopoulos et al, 2022), although it requires a developed industry capable of demanding (and affording) such analyses.

2. THE SOCIO ECONOMIC IMPACT OF AN IBA FACILITY IN BRAZIL

2.1. Environmental analysis

One of the Ion Beam Analytical methods, PIXE (Particle Induced X-ray Emission), was first proposed by Johansson, Akselsson, and Johansson (1970). They explored the X-ray energy dispersive capability of the newly developed Si(Li) solid-state detector by analyzing dust collected on a thin plastic sheet outside their laboratory window. To introduce PIXE technology at the University of São Paulo and support research on air pollution through elemental analysis of atmospheric aerosols, the PIXE-SP project was initiated in 1974 by Orsini, Netto and Tabacniks (1984). An irradiation chamber specially designed for analysis using the PIXE method was installed by Prof. C.M.Q. Orsini in the 8MV tandem-Pelletron laboratory of the Institute of Physics, in close collaboration with Prof. John W. Winchester, who ran a similar setup at Florida State University, USA. Soon, the PIXE-SP became a reference analytical method in a national air quality monitoring program led by the Group for Air Pollution Studies (GEPA) at IFUSP. The GEPA-SEMA project measured the air pollution in eight locations across Brazil, seven of which had critical air pollution problems and one in a pristine natural environment (Orsini et al, 1986; Tabacniks, Orsini and Artaxo, 1987). This was the first large scale use of a PIXE setup for air pollution assessment in Brazil. A key outcome was the installation of background air-pollution sampling stations at the Brazilian Antarctic Scientific Station (Wouters, Artaxo and Van Grieken, 1990) and in the Amazon Basin (Artaxo, P. et al, 1988), which continue to provide valuable data on local and biogenic Atmospheric Aerosols (Artaxo, 2019; Unfer et al, 2024). In 1990, the PIXE-SP setup was moved to the newly installed 1.7MV Tandem-Pelletron accelerator, which had also a dedicated RBS/NRA (Rutherford Backscattering and Nuclear Reaction Analysis) analytical setup. This new accelerator was purchased to support material analysis in general as part of a joint project between the Institute of Physics and the Engineering School of the University of São Paulo (Tabacniks, 2019). Research on air pollution contributed to the creation of the Laboratory for Atmospheric Physics (LFA Website, 2024), a leading group in Brazil that is also recognized worldwide. This research also advanced the LAMFI-USP, making IBA methods available to all researchers at the University of São Paulo (LAMFI Website, 2024).

In addition to its intensive use in atmospheric science and thin-film RBS analysis for the engineering school, LAMFI-USP applied IBA in several other fields of research. Martins et al. investigated the chronology of trace elements in the tree rings of a 166 ± 16 -year-old tree from the Amazon Basin using thick-target PIXE and proton backscattering analysis (Martins et al, 1999). They measured twenty-two elements along with the wood's density. The variability of trace element concentrations in the tree rings revealed significant environmental features, some of which could be linked to global

events during the tree's life. These included the 1815 eruption of the Tambora volcano, the onset of the Brazilian rubber boom in 1827, the 1883 eruption of the Krakatoa volcano, and a period of severe drought and biomass burning in the Amazon from 1911 to 1926. This study demonstrated the potential of trace elements analysis in tree rings for supporting paleoclimate research, linking local environmental data to global events.

2.2. Agriculture and food quality

Using Instrumental Neutron Activation Analysis and PIXE analysis, Medeiros et al (2005) found that genetically modified Brazilian soybean seeds had higher concentrations of Br, Ca, Cl, Cr, Mn, K, P, S, and Zn. Studies like this can contribute to broader analyses of the impact of genetically modified foods on daily diets, though requiring collaboration among multidisciplinary teams of experts.

2.3. Health and medical science

Serum samples from melanoma patients and a control group were analyzed for trace elements using PIXE and ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry) to explore whether trace elements could serve as diagnostic markers for cancer. Blood samples and clinical information were collected from 30 melanoma patients and 116 healthy donors at São Paulo Hospital (protocol CEP 1036/08 UNIFESP). Concentrations of K, S, Ca, and Se were found to be statistically different between the melanoma and control groups, after adjusting for clinical variables ($p \leq 0.05$). The findings highlighted the need to further stratify the data by age, gender, and cancer stage, which would require a substantial increase in the number of samples and the overall scope of the study. While additional research is necessary to develop this methodology into a practical diagnostic tool, the study provided a proof of concept for using IBA and other trace-element analytical techniques in the search for alternative cancer markers (Bernardes et al, 2014).

Another significant research outcome was the analysis of elemental content in baby teeth comparing preterm and full-term children (Takaoka, 2015). Samples were collected from 80 children aged 6 to 8 years, half of whom were born preterm. The preterm children had birth weights of less than 2.0 kg, while the full-term children weighed more than 2.45 kg. For trace-element analysis, PIXE, XRF (X-Ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy), and ICP-OES (Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry) were used complementarily. ICP-OES required a complete dissolution of the samples to measure the average composition of the whole tooth, while PIXE and XRF provided the elemental composition of the enamel. Results showed higher levels of Ca, P, Cu, and Zn in the enamel of the preterm group, along with significantly higher amounts of Sr in the whole teeth of premature children. These findings offer new insights into enamel mineralization in primary teeth and suggest possible metabolic changes in bone mineralization for preterm infants. Further research is needed to expand the data and explore the potential implications for the care of preterm children.

IBA was also used to support research and conduct toxicity tests on nanostructured mesoporous SBA-15 as a vaccine adjuvant (Martins, 2010; Scaramuzzi, 2016). SBA-15 silica is an inorganic material characterized by uniform hexagonal mesopores, each approximately 10 nm in diameter (Mariano-Neto et al, 2014). Its unique properties make it an ideal antigen delivery system, forming highly efficient immunogenic complexes (WIPO, 2007). The application of SBA-15 in oral vaccination represents a breakthrough in mass immunization with significant social impact. An oral vaccine against Hepatitis B has already been developed (Scaramuzzi et al, 2016), and similar advances are expected for diphtheria and tetanus. As part of a pre-clinical trial, PIXE analysis was

employed to investigate the accumulation of silicon (Si) in the organs of mice treated either orally or intramuscularly with silica powder. The analysis focused on detecting trace amounts of Si in calcined organs, specifically the spleen, lungs, liver, and kidneys, to determine the extent of silicon accumulation from SBA-15. The goal was to ensure the safe use of SBA-15 as a vaccine adjuvant by verifying its presence in the spleen over 35 days and its role in enhancing antibody formation. Additionally, the study verified minimal silicon agglomeration in the organs and its complete elimination through feces after 70 days.

2.4. Objects of cultural and archaeological interest

Ceramic objects are among the most common archaeological artifacts found during excavations. Their macroscopic and microscopic characteristics, along with trace elements, can provide valuable insights into manufacturing processes, the cultural development, the origin of raw materials, and trade networks. X-ray radiography and PIXE analysis were used to characterize a set of 36 pre-Hispanic ceramic pieces from the Chimu Culture, preserved at the Museum of Archaeology and Ethnology (MAE/USP). The analysis of trace elements, combined with X-ray tomography, helped identify manufacturing techniques and the granularity of the ceramics, facilitating the classification of the different cultures that once inhabited the site (Lima et al, 2011).

In a country like Brazil, tracing the history and habits of the original inhabitants provides a more comprehensive and accurate account of the nation's past and helps protecting their rights and well-being, a critical human rights issue. Understanding their history supports advocacy for their rights and offers additional data for comprehensive human rights discussions.

A recent study on decorative tiles of historical buildings in São Paulo used wide-field PIXE imaging to investigate the elemental composition of their pigments. Machine learning algorithms were applied to deconvolute overlapping signals and extract the spectra of the pure pigments (Silva et al, 2018). This case is particularly interesting because decorating buildings with tiles was not a common architectural practice in southern Brazil at the beginning of the 19th century; it was more typical in the northeast, influenced by the Dutch presence. Tracing the origin of these tiles could have revealed alternative trade routes and possible Dutch influence in the south. However, the study determined that the tiles were Portuguese, contradicting the theory of Dutch commerce in the region. This conclusion was made possible through the combination of IBA and machine learning for data analysis, which allowed the characterization of the blue pigment in the tiles, a key factor in determining their origin. This study highlights the cultural impact of IBA in uncovering aspects of Brazilian history.

2.5. Radiation tolerance tests of semiconductors

The CITAR Project (Portuguese acronym for Radiation Tolerant Integrated Circuits in Brazil) was established to create a Brazilian network focused on developing expertise and independence in designing, testing, and qualifying integrated circuits for operation in ionizing radiation environments. The existing Nuclear Physics Laboratory infrastructure at IFUSP was adapted to test circuits using protons and heavy ions, complementing the IEAv (Institute for Advanced Studies in São José dos Campos) facilities, which use neutrons, X-rays, and gamma rays. The experimental setup at IFUSP includes two tandem ion accelerators of 1.7 MV and 8 MV, irradiation stations, and testing electronics. Several circuits have been tested for radiation tolerance, including 3N163 transistors, power transistors, PIN diode solar cells, System on Module (SOM), Field Programmable Gate Arrays

(FPGAs), processors, memories, and Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) such as SpaceWire bus interfaces for satellites (Aguiar et al, 2014; Medina et al, 2014; 2016; Aguirre, 2017; Aguiar et al, 2020). Testing the effects of ionizing radiation on microcircuits is of vital importance and has significant technical and economic implications. This is a priority for the aerospace and communications industries, military applications, and the development of autonomous vehicles, all of which are vital for any nation determined for independence in the global air and space economy.

2.6. High-tech coatings and thin films

Energy-efficient cars are target for reducing carbon emissions and extending the battery life of electric vehicles. To enhance their energy efficiency, significant investments have been made in developing technological coatings that reduce friction in an engine. One promising candidate for this purpose is Diamond-Like Carbon (DLC). Whether doped or undoped, DLC films exhibit mechanical endurance and low friction. To analyze such materials, we developed a self-consistent approach that combines various IBA techniques to better characterize DLC films (Silva et al, 2013). DLC properties are sensitive to the hydrogen-to-carbon ratio and this analysis can serve as a quality control method as it also assesses the coverage area. When used in conjunction with PIXE, this method easily accounts for dopants providing a comprehensive characterization of DLC films.

From its beginning until around the year 2000, LAMFI-USP conducted systematic research on thin films containing Li, V, Ni, or Mo oxides. This research focused on developing new electrolyte materials for liquid or solid-state lithium batteries and electrochromic films, which are now used in the modern airplane windows (Ferreira, et al, 1996; Lourenço, et al, 1998; Faria, et al, 1998; Ferreira et al, 2000; Urbano et al, 2001; Kosminsky et al, 2003). ERDA (Elastic Recoil Detection Analysis) and Nuclear Reaction Analysis are among the few ion beam techniques capable of quantitatively detecting and profiling atomic hydrogen in solid materials, an effective method for measuring proton transport in thin films. Research on proton transport and thin film technologies collaborated for the development of lithium batteries for small devices, medical implants, and other applications where size is critical. Electrochromic windows, which can change their transparency by simply varying an applied voltage, are now readily available and used in both buildings and airplanes.

2.7. Energy and sustainability

Today, IBA plays an essential role in the research and development of fusion reactors, solar cells, and batteries. We contribute to national efforts in developing more efficient solar cells by providing high-quality thin-film analysis. Reliable analysis of multilayered thin-film structures requires the development of innovative data processing tools (Silva et al. 2016; 2021; 2022), along with improvements in the analytical setup and accelerator stability.

Technological challenges often push the boundaries of science. The development of a new generation of nuclear fusion reactors demands extensive analysis of internal walls, a significant challenge for IBA due to the vast amount of data required in a short time and the need for detailed characterization of surface deposits. Small accelerators used for IBA help advancing nuclear fusion by increasing analytical throughput, improving accuracy, and generating essential data (such as cross-sections and stopping powers) for a more comprehensive and reliable analysis of materials.

2.8. Microelectronics

From 2012 to 2024, the Engineering School of USP utilized LAMFI for Ion Beam Analysis in microelectronics research and development, accounting for approximately 12% of the total available analysis time. Research at the Engineering School focuses on the development of microelectronic devices, nanotechnology, thin films, waveguides, and memory devices. The primary applications requiring IBA include the manufacturing of Metal-Oxide-Semiconductors, Silicon-On-Insulator devices (Souza et al, 2021; Silva, Martino and Agopian, 2019; Souza et al, 2021; Bordallo et al, 2014), and thin films for semiconductor components and solar cells (Zambom and Mansano, 2015; Sparvoli et al, 2012). These applications involve materials such as semiconductor components and solar cells: SiO₂, Si₃N₄, Si_xO_yN_z, TiO₂, TiN, TiON, CrO₂, CrN, transparent conductors: ITO, AlO_{Fx}, SnO_{Fx}, and doped oxides: SiO₂-B₂O₃, SiO₂-P₂O₅. IBA has also been used for the analysis and quantification of Yb, Tm, and also Yb and Er in waveguides for applications in integrated photonics (Assumpção et al, 2017 ; Bonfim, 2016) and Te, Zn, and Au in thin films for memory applications (Bontempo et al. 2020).

Research on thin films and their applications at the Engineering School has made significant contributions to the technological development of semiconductors and microelectronics in general, while also playing a key role in training a significant number of engineers in Brazil.

2.9. Advancing IBA

Recognizing that solely providing high-quality Ion Beam Analysis services to external users falls short of the academic expectations for a university research laboratory, the LAMFI-USP research team has continually developed improvements in IBA over the years, contributing to the advancement of analytical techniques. One of these advancements is the development of a self-consistent IBA spectrum analysis software environment (Silva et al, 2021). Since 1999, SIMNRA has been the most widely used program for evaluating ion beam analysis data, processing both elastic and inelastic particle scattering data and nuclear reaction data (Mayer, 1999). However, SIMNRA is designed for single-spectrum analysis. To address this limitation, LAMFI-USP developed Multi-SIMNRA (Silva et al, 2016) a computational environment that allows and controls multiple instances of SIMNRA, searching for a unique sample composition that fits several spectra of the same sample simultaneously. It can manage a large number of variables, thus enhancing SIMNRA's fitting capabilities. Today, Multi-SIMNRA is used by over 291 users across 46 countries. Both SIMNRA and Multi-SIMNRA employ a bottom-up approach, starting with a target description and calculating the corresponding spectrum for comparison with actual data. In contrast, all available PIXE analysis software, such as PyMCA (Solé et al, 2007), GUPIX (Maxwell, Campbell and Teesdale, 1989) and others, use a mathematical model to fit a spectrum extracting peak areas and converting them to elemental masses. To integrate PIXE analysis into Multi-SIMNRA, we are currently developing a bottom-up PIXE analysis software, which will soon be released.

Analyzing thousands of samples using IBA remains a challenge, as IBA has traditionally been a one-sample-one-spectrum technique. The need for elemental imaging and processing of large numbers of samples led to the development of new approaches. Big Data, neural networks, and artificial intelligence technologies were adapted to process large sets of spectra that are largely similar with only minor variations (Silva et al, 2020; Guimarães et al, 2021). This initiative was further driven by the installation of the Large Area External Beam setup at LAMFI-USP in 2018 (Silva et al, 2018),

enabling elemental imaging of very large samples (Silva, Trindade, and Rizzutto, 2018) that generate thousands of spectra.

Built and installed at LAMFI-USP in 2018, the construction of the Large Area External Beam setup involved extensive collaboration among facility staff, local providers, and the manufacturing industry. The setup features a submillimeter ion beam, paired with a large, computer-controlled XYZ robotic stage. Its main attributes are a large range of 60 cm with 5 μm precision, for each axis and a combination of detectors that facilitate in-air PIXE, PIGE, NRA, and potentially RBS analysis. High-precision computer vision autofocus and image recognition compensate for micrometer-level irregularities in the sample's surface, reducing analytical artifacts. By recording the position of the analyzed spot, the sample's surface can also be reconstructed, generating 3D compositional maps. This setup currently serves as the flagship of LAMFI-USP for PIXE analysis of various samples, including fossils, wood, sediments, speleothems, ceramics, and paintings, with easy "in-air" sample handling. These improvements were driven by the real analytical demands of IBA users, creating valuable opportunities to advance IBA methodologies.

2.10. Basic Science

The IBA community depends on well-established global databases of e.g. X-ray emission lines and cross sections for X-rays, protons, alpha particles, gamma rays, as well as proton and alpha stopping powers, among other related parameters for accurate results. In addition to careful calibration with elemental samples or Certified Reference Materials (CRMs), participation in Round Robin exercises, where unknown samples distributed by accredited laboratories are analyzed, is another important method for ensuring the accuracy of an IBA setup (Barradas et al, 2005). Once confidence is established and the analytical setups were accredited, the laboratory contributed to international databases by measuring cross sections (Matias et al, 2024), and stopping powers (Moro et al, 2016). These contributions advance the overall knowledge of IBA, while also providing valuable training for young scientists and encouraging international collaboration.

2.11. Science education and outreach

LAMFI-USP is frequently invited to assist with undergraduate courses on modern physics, nuclear physics, particle accelerators, nuclear instrumentation, and ion beam analysis. Recently, the laboratory was utilized to replicate the Cockcroft-Walton (1932) experiment, in which the ${}^7\text{Li}(p,\alpha){}^4\text{He}$ reaction was artificially produced for the first time. Students successfully recreated the experiment using the regular RBS setup. This nuclear reaction, with its high Q-value, is particularly effective for demonstrating Einstein's mass-energy equivalence. It also serves as an excellent illustration of Gamow's tunneling theory (Gamow, 1929) essential for understanding the experiment. Another popular outreach activity for visitors is called "*The Atomic Detective*" where the general public is challenged to measure the composition of everyday objects (e.g., wristwatches, wedding rings) by performing a qualitative PIXE analysis using the external beam setup.

In summary, small particle accelerators are unique facilities where students at different educational levels can experience the daily work of a scientist firsthand. For high school students, visiting and exploring experiments in such a facility can inspire them to pursue careers in science. For undergraduate students, access to such a facility serve as training platforms to develop essential technical skills. In both cases, the impact on science education can be profound.

3. DISCUSSION

Assessing the socio-economic impact of small accelerator facilities is inherently challenging, given their broad range of applications and interdisciplinary scope. Over more than 30 years of continuous operation, the Ion Beam Analysis (IBA) facility at the University of São Paulo has contributed significantly to diverse research areas—including environmental science, archaeology, solar energy, thin-film materials, and radiation-hardened microelectronics. Beyond supporting scientific advancement, the facility has also played an important role in education and outreach, offering hands-on training and fostering scientific engagement across academic and public audiences.

3.1. Socioeconomic Impact and Technological Readiness in LAMFI-USP Activities

A key factor behind LAMFI-USP's long-standing success in collaborating with a broad scientific community lies in its organizational model. Departing from the traditional Nuclear Physics Program Advisory Committee (PAC), LAMFI adopted a simplified, user-oriented system in which researchers submit analysis requests through an online form at any time (LAMFI Website, 2024). Experiments are scheduled primarily on a first-come, first-served basis, an essential feature for materials science projects constrained by tight timelines. For complex or unconventional samples, scheduling is flexible and based on consultations with LAMFI's technical team. These requests, combined with experimental data, serve as inputs for laboratory and user statistics.

From its beginning, LAMFI-USP has provided online access to all spectra generated, reinforcing transparency and user autonomy, well before the current “*open data*” policy. Over 30 years, approximately 500 users, including students, researchers, and industry representatives, have conducted Ion Beam Analysis at the facility, developing both technical skills and scientific insight. Additionally, difficulties in sourcing parts and services for the accelerator, motivated the development of in-house expertise. Today, despite its small team, LAMFI maintains and upgrades its own accelerator infrastructure and beamlines, ensuring continuous innovation.

In the context of an emerging country, LAMFI's most enduring contribution is the training of qualified human resources. Through hands-on access to advanced instrumentation and collaborative projects, young researchers gain the experience needed to participate in international research efforts. As Waterman noted in the preface to Bush's seminal *Science, the Endless Frontier* (Bush, 1945) “*Economic growth and industrial innovation depend on rich resources of basic knowledge, and the full development of researchers requires sustained support for basic research*”. Beyond scientific training, LAMFI has also contributed to public engagement. Projects such as scientific outreach activities and laboratory visits have sparked interest in physics and promoted broader appreciation for science.

3.2. Socioeconomic impact and TRL

Measuring the socioeconomic impact of scientific research remains a challenge, especially for facilities dedicated to basic science. One possible proxy is the Technological Readiness Level (TRL) scale, first introduced by NASA by Mankins (1995) and generally adopted by funding agencies and industries to evaluate the maturity of technological developments. TRLs range from fundamental research (TRL 1) to full-scale deployment (TRL 9). Although TRL was not designed as a metric for socioeconomic impact, each level inherently represents cumulative progress with increasing practical relevance.

Bornmann (2013) identifies two research modalities: (1) academically driven, focused on excellence and theoretical advances, and (2) transdisciplinary, aimed at solving real-world problems and generating societal, environmental, or technological value. The latter mode is harder to quantify: societal impacts are diffuse, long-term, and often lack clear causality. Case studies remain the most accepted form of impact assessment. Until reliable quantitative tools emerge, qualitative evaluations by expert panels are recommended, ideally involving both scientists and stakeholders (e.g., policymakers, industry professionals). Interestingly, researchers are often unaware of their work's broader societal impact. Until robust quantitative methods are available, expert panels are recommended for assessing societal relevance. These panels should not be composed solely of scientists, as researchers may struggle to identify real-world applications. While assessing research impact is crucial for guiding investment and strengthening innovation systems, it must be acknowledged that research inherently explores the unknown. This unpredictability means that serendipity often plays a central role in the significance of research outcomes.

3.3. Socio-Economic Impact and TRL

While we are not specialists in impact evaluation, we propose a simple quantitative approach to support expert judgment. Since higher TRLs include all earlier development stages, the Socio-Economic Impact (SEI) of a given TRL can be approximated by the square of its TRL value, normalized to a maximum reference value. This yields a Socio-Economic Impact Index (SEII) ranging from 0 to 1. This formulation is a consequence of the well-known sum of consecutive integers, which grows proportionally to the square of the final term¹. The choice of the maximum reference TRL value (8.5) is explained below. Given LAMFI's nature as a basic research facility with diverse applications, we adopted a simplified TRL classification proposed by Carulla et al (2024), which groups TRLs into four categories:

Prototyping (TRL 1–4, average 2.5)

Piloting (TRL 5–6, average 5.5)

Demonstration (TRL 7)

Deployment (TRL 8–9, average 8.5)

Each IBA application conducted at LAMFI was assigned a TRL according to this scheme. For topics with more than one outcome, the highest TRL was used. **Table 1** presents the preceding topics and their corresponding simplified Carulla's averaged TRL in paragraph order. The resulting SEI values were averaged, producing an overall SEII of **0.53**. Although preliminary, and requiring refinement by a qualified committee, this approach offers a quantitative index for assessing socioeconomic relevance. Notably, applications in medical and technological fields yielded the highest SEIs, though the advancement of IBA itself also exhibits substantial impact. As emphasized by Bush (1945), even research at low TRLs plays a critical role in economic development and must be consistently supported. This underscores the importance of sustaining laboratories like LAMFI that bridge fundamental science and applied research through training, infrastructure, and innovation.

¹ The sum $1 + 2 + \dots + n = n(n + 1)/2 \sim n^2$.

Table 1: Simplified TRL and corresponding SEI of the activities at LAMFI-USP, adapting the definitions of Carulla et al. (2024). **TRL:** Technological Readiness Level, **SEI** : Normalized Socio-Economic Impact.

Paragraph	Context	Averaged TRL	SEI = $(\text{TRL}/8.5)^2$
2.1	Environmental analysis	7.0	0.68
2.2	Agriculture and food quality	2.5	0.09
2.3	Health and medical science	8.5	1.00
2.4	Objects with cultural and archaeological interest	2.5	0.09
2.5	Radiation tolerance tests of semiconductors	5.5	0.42
2.6	High-tech coatings and thin films	8.5	1.00
2.7	Energy and sustainability	5.5	0.42
2.8	Microelectronics	8.5	1.00
2.9	Advancing IBA	8.5	1.00
2.10	Basic Science	2.5	0.09
2.11	Science education and outreach	2.5	0.09
		average	0.53

4. CONCLUSIONS

The socio-economic impacts of research activities, particularly those carried out in an Ion Beam Analysis (IBA) laboratory, refer to possible societal outcomes such as improvements in quality of life, economic development, workforce qualification, job creation, and environmental sustainability. To promote discussion on this topic, the International Atomic Energy Agency organized a Technical Meeting on Novel Applications of Accelerator-Based Techniques for Socio-Economic Benefits (IAEA, 2023). The meeting emphasized the social relevance of ion accelerators and reinforced the recognized challenge of quantifying the socio-economic impact of scientific research.

In this work, we proposed a simple, quantitative framework to support impact assessment, extending the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) introduced by Mankins (1995). Using a simplified four-level classification proposed by Carulla et al. (2024) we suggest that, while TRLs are not direct measures of socio-economic impact, they capture the cumulative technological progress and efforts. Hence, we defined a Socio-Economic Impact (SEI) metric as the square of the TRL value, normalized to the maximum level (in this case 8.5). This formulation assumed that the investment required to achieve higher TRLs is nonlinear. The Socio-Economic Impact Index (SEII) is then defined as the average SEI across all laboratory activities, providing a relative measure of socio-economic value. Although this index is not intended as a measure of scientific productivity, it may assist strategic planning and evaluation. For instance, comparing SEI values can guide decisions on whether to maintain or discontinue specific applications. However, planning future developments is inherently uncertain. Scientific judgment, experience, and vision remain essential in defining research priorities and the laboratory’s trajectory.

Based on these considerations, future work at LAMFI-USP will focus on advancing IBA methods and improving the underlying databases: developing time-resolved IBA for studying solid-state chemical reactions, gas-surface interactions, and catalytic processes relevant to CO₂ conversion and carbon-neutral technologies; continue investigating radiation damage in solids, particularly the

formation of color centers in diamond, contributing to the understanding of quantum materials and sensors; perform environmental analysis of microplastics and flame retardants to assess their spread and biological effects; and refine the IBA databases with data on stopping power near the Bragg peak in low Z elements, to enhance safety and dose control in proton therapy.

Finally, we recommend that national agencies and funding bodies support open and inclusive access to IBA facilities for students and researchers. Programs like the Coordinated Research Project G42008-2019 (IAEA, 2018) may serve as a valuable model for supporting research laboratories and building collaborative innovation.

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REFERENCES

- Agopian, P. et al. (2013). Stress engineering and proton radiation influence on off-state leakage current in triple-gate SOI devices. *Solid-State Electronics*, 90, pp.155–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sse.2013.02.037>
- Aguiar, A.P.V. et al. (2014). Experimental setup for Single Event Effects at the São Paulo 8UD Pelletron Accelerator. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 332, pp.397–400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2014.02.105>
- Aguiar, A.P.V. et al. (2020). A heavy-ion multi-purpose irradiation facility in Brazil. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 91(5), 053301. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5138644>
- Aguirre, F.R. (2017). *Estudo sobre distribuição de cargas em semicondutores sujeitos a radiação ionizante*. MSc thesis (in Portuguese), University of São Paulo.
- Artaxo, P. (2019). Working together for Amazonia. *Science*, 363, p.323. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaw6986>
- Artaxo, P. et al. (1988). Composition and Sources of Aerosols from the Amazon Basin. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 93, pp.1605–1615. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JD093iD02p01605>
- Assumpção, T.A.A. et al. (2017). Influence of gold nanoparticles on the 805 nm gain in $\text{Tm}^{3+}/\text{Yb}^{3+}$ codoped PbO-GeO_2 pedestal waveguides. *Optical Materials*, 72, pp.518–523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2017.06.031>

- Barradas, N. et al. (2005). A round robin characterization of the thickness and composition of thin to ultra-thin AlNO films. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 227, pp.397–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2004.08.021>
- Bernal, J.D. (1939). *The social function of science*. London: George Routledge & Sons Ltd.
- Bernardes, S., Tabacniks, M.H., Santos, D.A.O., Oliveira, F.A., Shie, N.J., Sarkis, E.S. and Oliveira, T. (2014). Ascertaining serum levels of trace elements in melanoma patients using PIXE and HR-ICPMS. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 318, pp.178–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2013.06.064>
- Bonfim, A.F. (2016). *Determination of the concentration of Yb and Er elements in GeO₂-PO thin films on a pedestal waveguide covered by gold nanoparticles for application at 1532 nm*. PhD thesis (in Portuguese).
- Bontempo, L. et al. (2020). Process oxygen flow influence on the structural properties of thin films obtained by co-sputtering of (TeO₂)_x-ZnO and Au onto Si substrates. *Nanomaterials*, 10, p.1863. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10091863>
- Bordallo, C.M. et al. (2014). Analog performance of standard and uniaxial strained triple-gate SOI FinFETs under x-ray radiation. *Semiconductor Science and Technology*, 29, p.125015. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0268-1242/29/12/125015>
- Bornmann, L. (2013). What is societal impact of research and how can it be assessed? A literature survey. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 64(2), pp.217–233. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.22803>
- Bush, V. (1945). *Science, the Endless Frontier*. National Science Foundation, USA.
- Carulla, L.S., Woods, C., de Miquel, C. and Lukersmith, S. (2024). Adaptation of the technology readiness levels for impact assessment in implementation sciences: The TRL-IS checklist. *Heliyon*, 10, e29930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e29930>
- Charisopoulos, S., Ridikas, D., Horak, C. and Starovoitova, V. (2022). *International Conference on Accelerators for Research and Sustainable Development: From Good Practices Towards Socio-economic Impact*, 23–27 May, Vienna, Austria. Available at: <https://www.iaea.org/events/acconf22>
- Coccia, M. (2018). *Socio-economic driving forces of scientific research*. CocciaLab Working Paper No. 35/bis. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1806.05028>
- Cockcroft, J.D. and Walton, E.T.S. (1932). Experiments with high velocity positive ions. II. The disintegration of elements by high velocity protons. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A*, 137, pp.229–242. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1930.0169>
- Faria, I.C. et al. (1998). Towards Efficient Electrochromic NiO_x Films: A Study of microstructure, morphology and stoichiometry. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 145, pp.235–240. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1838240>
- Ferreira, F.F. et al. (1996). Electrochromic Nickel Oxide Thin Film Deposited Under Different Sputtering Conditions. *Solid State Ionics*, 86, pp.971–976. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.448243>
- Ferreira, F.F. et al. (2000). Lithium Insertion and Electrochromism in Polycrystalline Molybdenum Oxide Films. *Solid State Ionics*, 136, pp.357–363. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2738\(00\)00483-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2738(00)00483-5)

Gamow, G. (1929). Zur Quantentheorie der Atomzertrümmerung. *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 52, pp.510–515. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01339451>

Guimarães, R.S. et al. (2021). Processing of massive Rutherford Backscattering Spectrometry data by artificial neural networks. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 493, pp.28–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2021.02.010>

International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). (2018). *New CRP: Facilitating Experiments with Ion Beam Accelerators – G42008*. Available at: <https://www.iaea.org/newscenter/news/new-crp-facilitating-experiments-with-ion-beam-accelerators-g42008>

International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), December (2023). *Technical Meeting on Novel Applications of Accelerator-based Techniques for Socio-economic Benefits* (EVT2205716) <https://www.iaea.org/events/evt2205716>

Johansson, T.B., Akselsson, K.R. and Johansson, S.A.E. (1970). X-ray analysis: Elemental trace analysis at the 10^{-12} g level. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*, 84, pp.141. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X\(70\)90751-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X(70)90751-2)

Kosminsky, L. et al. (2003). Electrochemical codeposition of platinum and molybdenum oxides: Formation of composite films with distinct electrocatalytic activity for hydrogen peroxide detection. *Electroanalysis*, 15, pp.733–738. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elan.200390092>

LAMFI Website (2024) Applications and Analysis. Available at: <https://portal.if.usp.br/lamfi/en/node/370>

LFA Website. (2024). Available at: <https://lfa.if.usp.br/>

Lima, S.C., Rizzutto, M.A., Added, N., Barbosa, D.L.M., Trindade, G.F. and Fleming, I.D.A. (2011). Pre-Hispanic ceramics analyzed using PIXE and radiographic techniques. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 269, pp.3025–3031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2011.04.064>

Lourenço, A. et al. (1998). Radio-frequency reactively sputtered VOx thin films deposited at different oxygen flows. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 145, pp.706–711. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1838327>

Mankins, J.C. (1995). *Technology Readiness Levels: A White Paper*. Office of Space Access and Technology, NASA.

Mariano-Neto, F. et al. (2014). Physical properties of ordered mesoporous SBA-15 silica as immunological adjuvant. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, 47, p.425402. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/47/42/425402>

Martins, J.V., Artaxo, P., Ferraz, E.S.B. and Tabacniks, M.H. (1999). Chronological studies of tree-rings from the Amazon Basin using thick target PIXE and proton backscattering analysis. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 150(1), pp.240–247. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-583X\(98\)01035-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-583X(98)01035-0)

- Martins, T.S. et al. (2010). Synthesis, characterization and catalytic evaluation of cubic ordered mesoporous iron-silicon oxides. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 124, pp.713–719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2010.07.042>
- Matias, F. et al. (2024). Efficient computational modeling of electronic stopping power of organic polymers for proton therapy optimization. *Scientific Reports*, 14, p.9868. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-60651-0>
- Maxwell, J.A., Campbell, J.L. and Teesdale, W.J. (1989). The Guelph PIXE Software Package. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 43, pp.218–230. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X\(89\)90042-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X(89)90042-6)
- Mayer, M. (1999). SIMNRA, a simulation program for the analysis of NRA, RBS and ERDA. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 475. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.59188>
- Medeiros, M.M.A., Zamboni, B.C., Medeiros, A.G.J., Rizzutto, M.A., Added, N. and Tabacniks, M.H. (2005). Multi-elemental analysis of genetically modified food using ANAA and PIXE techniques. *Brazilian Journal of Physics*, 35(3B), pp.814–817. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0103-97332005000500025>
- Medina, N.H. et al. (2014). First Successful SEE Measurements with Heavy Ions in Brazil. *IEEE Radiation Effects Data Workshop*, pp.1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1109/REDW.2014.7004571>
- Medina, N.H. et al. (2016). Experimental Setups for Single Event Effect Studies. *Journal of Nuclear Physics, Material Sciences, Radiation and Applications*, 4(1), pp.13–23. <https://doi.org/10.15415/jnp.2016.41002>
- Moro, M. et al. (2016). Traceable stopping cross sections of Al and Mo elemental targets for 0.9–3.6-MeV protons. *Physical Review A*, 93, 022704. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.93.022704>
- Orsini, C.M.Q., Tabacniks, M.H., Artaxo, P., Andrade, M.F. and Kerr, A.S. (1986). Characteristics of Fine and Coarse Particles of Natural and Urban Aerosol of Brazil. *Atmospheric Environment*, 20, pp.2259–2269. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981\(86\)90316-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-6981(86)90316-1)
- Orsini, C.Q., Netto, P.A. and Tabacniks, M.H. (1984). The São Paulo PIXE system and its use on a national monitoring air quality program. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 3(1), pp.462–465. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X\(84\)90418-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X(84)90418-X)
- Scaramuzzi, K. et al. (2016). Nanostructured SBA-15 silica: An effective protective vehicle for oral hepatitis B vaccine immunization. *Nanomedicine: Nanotechnology, Biology and Medicine*, 12, pp.2241–2250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nano.2016.06.003>
- Silva, T.F. et al. (2013). Ion beam analysis of a-C:H films on alloy steel substrate. *Thin Solid Films*, 545, pp.171–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2013.07.073>
- Silva, T.F. et al. (2016). MultiSIMNRA: A computational tool for self-consistent ion beam analysis using SIMNRA. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 371, pp.86–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2015.10.038>
- Silva, T.F. et al. (2018). Elemental mapping of large samples by external ion beam analysis with sub-millimeter resolution and its applications. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research*

Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms, 422, pp.68–77.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2018.03.006>

Silva, T.F. et al. (2021). Self-consistent ion beam analysis: An approach by multi-objective optimization. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 506, pp.32–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2021.09.007>

Silva, T.F., Rodrigues, C.L., Tabacniks, M.H. et al. (2020). Ion beam analysis and big data: How data science can support next-generation instrumentation. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 478, pp.111–115.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2020.05.027>

Silva, T.F., Rodrigues, C.L., Tabacniks, M.H., Toussaint, U. and Mayer, M. (2022). Bias and synergy in the self-consistent approach of data analysis of ion beam techniques. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 533, pp.9–16.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nimb.2022.10.008>

Silva, T.F., Trindade, G.F. and Rizzutto, M.A. (2018). Multivariate analysis applied to particle-induced X-ray emission mapping. *X-Ray Spectrometry*, 47(5), pp.372–381.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/xrs.2953>

Silva, V., Martino, J. and Agopian, P. (2019). Analysis of Omega-Gate Nanowire Devices from Parasitic Conduction to Ionizing Radiation Effects. *ECS Journal of Solid State Science and Technology*, 8, pp.Q54–Q60. <https://doi.org/10.29292/jics.v15i1.113>

Solé, V.A., Papillon, E., Cotte, M., Walter, Ph. and Susini, J. (2007). A multiplatform code for the analysis of energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectra. *Spectrochimica Acta Part B: Atomic Spectroscopy*, 62, pp.63–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sab.2006.12.002>

Souza, R.N. de B. et al. (2021). Voltage gain improvement of the operational transconductance amplifier designed with silicon-on-insulator FinFET after being exposed to proton-irradiation. *Semiconductor Science and Technology*, 36, p.035001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6641/abd349>

Sparvoli, M. et al. (2012). Optical and electrical properties of sputtered InNO thin films. *Physica Status Solidi (C)*, 9, pp.1384–1387. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssc.201100518>

Tabacniks, M.H. (2019). The Laboratory of Material Analysis with Ion Beams, LAMFI-USP. *arXiv preprint*. arXiv:1902.08309. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1902.08309>

Tabacniks, M.H., Orsini, C. and Artaxo, P. (1987). PIXE analysis for air pollution source apportionment in urban areas of Brazil. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 22(1), pp.315–318.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X\(87\)90348-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-583X(87)90348-X)

Takaoka, A.M.V. (2015). *Conteúdo mineral do esmalte de dentes decíduos de crianças nascidas pré-termo e a termo*. PhD thesis (in Portuguese), UNIFESP. Available at:

<https://repositorio.unifesp.br/handle/11600/47974>

Unfer, G.R. et al. (2024). Amazonian aerosol size distributions in a lognormal phase space: characteristics and trajectories. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 24, pp.3869–3882.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-24-3869-2024>

Urbano, A. et al. (2001). Electronic structure of Li_xNiO_y thin films. *Journal of Power Sources*, 97, pp.328–331. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(01\)00680-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(01)00680-2)

World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). (2007). *International Patent WO 07030901*.

Wouters, L., Artaxo, P. and Van Grieken, R. (1990). Laser Microprobe Mass Analysis of Individual Antarctic Aerosol Particles. *Atmospheric Environment*, 38, pp.427–438. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03067319008026946>

Zambom, L.S. and Mansano, R.D. (2015). p-ZnO Thin Films Deposited by RF-Magnetron Sputtering. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 591, p.012040. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/591/1/012040>